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Level of Awareness of G12-HUMSS Students in the Current Social Issues

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of awareness of G12 students in Tanay Senior High School when it comes to the current social issues that besets our nation. The respondents of the study are the Grade 12 students of Tanay Senior High School for the SY. 2021-2022. They were determined through availability sampling and the target population is over 50% of the total Grade 12 population. A quantitative descriptive type of research will be used in the study to determine the respondent's appraisal of the abovementioned program. The study will utilize a researcher-made questionnaire checklist which will be validated by the Master Teachers. Two areas of concern will be raised in the study; first contains the profile of the respondents which are their news source, and available reading materials at home. The second part will be the determining aspects on the level of awareness on particular social issues that are happening in our country such as a.) extra-judicial killings connected to the President's drug war; b.) proliferation of fake news and historical revisionism; c.) territorial disputes in the West Philippine Sea; and d.) human rights and freedom of expression.

Keywords: *teaching and learning, social sciences, current, student interests and motivation*

Introduction

Public opinion is shaped by awareness on certain issues that are happening around us. Its significance is very much evident as seen in the results elections, public outcry and even revolutions. Swaying public opinion into someone's favor is heavily advantageous to the one holding the narrative, whether it is the truth or not.

That is why it is important for people to be aware of the current issues that concerns their particular group, locality and their own country. Because if we are not aware of these particular issues, we can be easily swayed by the narrative of individuals with covert motives. As the famous author, Mark Twain puts it, "It is not what we do not know that get's us into trouble. It is what we know, that just isn't so."

Recent studies show that Filipinos, while ranking low on perceiving key global issues, are somehow very much confident about their opinion on these issues. The Philippines has landed in the company of Brazil, and South Africa as the "most ignorant" countries due to inaccurate perceptions on key issues, Indy100 reports. The attention-grabbing headline is based on the Ipsos Perils of Perception report released in December 2017, which "highlights how wrong the online public across 38 countries are about key global issues and features of the population in their country."

A Dunning and Kruger study (1999) showed that people with the lowest in cognitive tasks always statistically overestimated how well they did. Aligned with this, a 2017 study on the Perils of Perception, among 38 countries, showed Filipinos to be the 3rd most ignorant of key issues, and yet among the most confident that they are right.

This phenomenon is called the Dunning-Kruger effect, where people always overestimate their perception of their own knowledge due to, say, overconfidence. In psychology, the Dunning-Kruger effect is a cognitive bias whereby people with limited knowledge or competence in a given intellectual or social domain greatly overestimate their own knowledge or competence in that domain relative to objective criteria or to the performance of their peers or of people in general. The Macmillan Dictionary defines it as "the phenomenon by which an incompetent person is too incompetent to understand his own competence." More competent people, on the other hand, acknowledge their limitations and might play down their expertise.

The sad part of this reality is that Filipinos are confident despite having limited know-how on key issues.

Perhaps the reason why Filipinos are not accurate in terms of their knowledge on key issues is that they don't find topics such as history, politics, economics, law and such as interesting subjects to delve into deeper.

The Social Sciences are always one of the least favorite subjects before and even in the present.

Back in 1982, a survey was taken of sixth and 12th-graders in a Midwest school district to determine how the students felt about social studies. The results: The kids were "largely indifferent" or revealed "negative attitudes" toward social studies. If you listen to students and teachers, not much has changed since: A lot of kids in K-12 schools find history class boring.

The question now is, how can we make the Social Sciences a more attractive subject to our students, who at most, will be the future shapers of public discourse in our country?

This study aims to find out first the level of awareness of the students in terms of the current social issues that shape today's public opinion. After this, the researcher will use this as a basis for developing a program that can help improve this awareness to our students.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the quantitative-descriptive research design in this basic study.

Respondents

This study used the purposive sampling technique. The aim is to gather data from the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Science students, whose area of specialization involves learning about the social sciences, including current events that reflects our current social climate.

Instrument

The researcher used a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist to gather data from the chosen respondents. The names of the respondents were subjected to confidentiality in order to protect their data from unnecessary leakage.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data collected by the researcher, a statistician was consulted to help aid in the completion of this research. Upon the recommendation of the statistician, mean and frequency of responses were used to interpret the result of this study.

Results and Discussion

Upon gathering the data, the following results are presented:

Table 1. *Profile of the respondents in terms of Available Source of News at Home*

<i>Available Source of News at Home</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>%</i>
Television	40	100
Radio	8	20
Social Media Platforms	35	87.5
Newspaper	5	12.5

In the profile of the respondents, 40 students or all of the respondents answered that the available source of news in their homes was the Television, garnering the highest total frequency of responses with a percentage of 100%. It is followed by the Social Media Platforms, which garnered the total frequency of responses at 35 and stands at 87.5 percent.

Radio and Newspapers got the lowest number of responses with 8 and 5 respectively. This signifies that the 21st century learners of today prefer getting their news from the television and different social media platforms, which is the most available source among them. On the other hand, Radio and Newspaper got the lowest number of responses due to the fact that most of them doesn't have access to these mediums. This source can also be considered "old school" for them, which has an effect on their interest in using such mediums.

Political

Table 2. *Level of Awareness as Perceived by Grade 12 HUMSS Students in terms of Political Issues*

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Extra-judicial killings connected to the President's drug war	3.35	Much Aware
2. Proliferation of fake news and historical revisionism	3.13	Much Aware
3. Territorial disputes in the West Philippine Sea	3.5	Much Aware
4. Human rights and freedom of expression	3.83	Very Much Aware
5. Red-tagging and suppression of dissent	3	Much Aware

For the Level of Awareness as Perceived by Grade 12 HUMSS Students on the Current Social Issues, it is divided into 3 parts, namely; a. Political, b. Economic and c. Gender Equality. These aspects were chosen because they are the issues that the researcher thinks are close to their own experiences and belief.

For the Political aspect, the issue of human rights and freedom of expression got the highest mean score with 3.83 and interpreted verbally as Very Much Aware. This means that the respondents are very much aware of issues regarding human rights and freedom of expression.

On the other hand, the political issue regarding Red-tagging and suppression of dissent against the critics of the government got the lowest mean score of 3.00, interpreted verbally as Much Aware.

This shows that Grade 12 HUMSS students are aware of the issue that those voices critical of the government are now allegedly experience harassment from state forces and suppression of their basic right to self-expression, though they don't give much weight on it compared to the previous issue discussed.

Economic

Table 3. *Level of Awareness as Perceived by Grade 12 HUMSS Students in terms of Economic Issues*

Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. rising prices of basic commodities	3.53	Very Much Aware
2. unemployment in the Philippines pushes Filipinos to look for work abroad	3.73	Very Much Aware
3. Traffic situation and its effect on our economy	3.75	Very Much Aware
4. Shortage of agricultural supplies	3.5	Much Aware
5. Rising inflation rate	3.5	Much Aware

For the Economic issues, the issue of the Traffic Situation and its Effect on the Economy got the highest mean score, with 3.75, closely by the issue of Unemployment in the Philippines that pushes Filipinos to work Abroad, with 3.73, both verbally interpreted as Very Much Aware. This shows that these particular issues are very much relevant to the lives of the respondents.

Meanwhile, both the issue of shortage of Agricultural Supplies and the Rising Inflation Rate got the lowest mean in the group with 3.5 and can be interpreted verbally as Much Aware. It can be gleaned that the respondents are aware in this issue those they are not showing much attention to it as much as the previous issue tackled in this aspect.

Gender Equality

Table 4. *Level of Awareness as Perceived by Grade 12 HUMSS Students in terms of Gender Equality Issues*

Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Discrimination of members of the LGBTQA+	3.73	Very Much Aware
2. Safe Spaces Act of 2021	2.93	Aware
3. Sexual abuse that women experienced in work and public places	3.70	Very Much Aware
4. Stereotypes against women and members of the LGBTQA + communities	3.55	Very Much Aware
5. Physical and mental abuse subjected to women	3.75	Very Much Aware

As for the Gender Equality Aspect, the issue pertaining to the Physical Abuse subjected to Women gained an average mean of 3.75 and is verbally interpreted as Very Much Aware. It means that the respondents are very much aware that women are still subjected to different kinds of abuse even to this day.

On the other hand, the issue pertaining to Safe Spaces Act of 2019 or commonly known as the “Anti-Bastos Law” got the lowest mean score at 2.93. This means that the respondents are Aware that provisions of this law will help prevent abuses to women in public and work places. It can even be gleaned that only a handful of respondents may not be aware that such a law even exists.

Table 5. *Level of Awareness as Perceived by Grade 12 HUMSS Students in the Current Social Issues*

Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Political	3.36	Aware
Economic	3.6	Very Much Aware
Gender Equality	3.53	Aware

It can be gleaned from the table that among the three aspects used in the study, the economic aspect got the highest mean score of 3.6 and can be interpreted as Very Much Aware. It is followed by the Gender Equality Aspect, which garnered a mean score of 3.53, interpreted verbally as Very Much Aware. The Political aspect got the lowest mean score, standing at 3.36 but overall, is interpreted as Much Aware.

If will be given extensive thought, it can be viewed that among the aspects discussed in the study, the Economic and Gender Equality Issues got the higher score due to the fact that the respondents might be viewing these issues as more relevant to them, because these issues are much closer to their stomachs.

Table 6. *Frequency of responses on the factors that affect awareness of Grade 12 HUMSS students on the different Social Issues.*

What affects your awareness on the different social issues	Frequency (f)	%
Interest	26	65
Availability of News Materials	18	45
Relevance to your Life	17	42.5
Influence from peers, parents and others	23	57.5
Influence from the academe (teacher/classmates)	13	32.5

From the table, we can interpret that the main factor that affects the awareness of Grade 12 HUMSS students on the different social issues is Interest which holds the highest number of frequencies at 26. The second factor would be Influence from peers, parents and other with the frequency of 23.

The least factor which garnered the lowest frequency at 13 is Influence from the academe. This shows that among all the factors

indicated, influence from the teachers and other members of the academe is the least of the consideration that the respondents take into account.

This is a sad reality, wherein most members of the academe should have been the most trusted source of learning, students nowadays seem to give more importance to the interesting alternative facts they see on social media.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the HUMSS students from Tanay Senior High School displayed a high level of awareness in terms of the current social issues in our society. This affirms the fact that they chose to enter the HUMSS strand precisely because they have interests in subjects related to social and political sciences.

One of the recommendations received by this study is to apply this study to non-HUMSS students to learn how aware are they of the current social and political issues. Tanay Senior High School offers a wide array of strands within the Academic and TVL tracks, and they could be the next specimen of this study.

Also, as part of the core subjects being offered to all SHS students, we should make subjects like Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics (UCSP) more interesting to students so they may take more interest in studying Politics and other issues surrounding it.

Another recommendation received from experts suggests that social science teachers should relate current events to the everyday lives of the students so they can see the relevance of it in their own lives.

Furthermore, it is highly recommended to relate local events to national events so they can see the connection between the current events happening nationally in our lives.

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